

Machine Learning Models Predict the Need of Amputation and/or Peripheral Artery Revascularization in Hypertensive Patients Within 7-Years Follow-Up *

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Abstract— Lower extremity amputation and requirement of peripheral artery revascularization are common outcomes of undiagnosed peripheral artery disease patients. In this work, prediction models for the need of amputation or peripheral revascularization focused on hypertensive patients within seven years follow up are employed. We applied machine learning (ML) models using classifiers such as Extreme Gradient Boost (XGBoost), Random Forest (RF) and Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost), that will allow clinicians to identify the patients at risk of these two endpoints using simple clinical data. We utilized the non-interventional cohort of the getABI study in the primary care setting, selecting 4,191 hypertensive patients out of 6,474 patients with age over 65 years old and followed up for vascular events or death up to 7 years. During this follow up period, 150 patients underwent either amputation or peripheral revascularization or both. Accuracy, Specificity, Sensitivity and Area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) were estimated for each machine learning model. The results demonstrate Random Forest as the most accurate model for the prediction of the composite endpoint in hypertensive patients within 7 years follow-up, achieving 73.27 % accuracy.

Keywords—Machine Learning Models, Amputation, Peripheral Artery Revascularization, Risk Factors

Clinical Relevance—This study assists clinicians to better predict and treat these serious outcomes, amputation and peripheral revascularization in hypertensive patients.

I. INTRODUCTION

The peripheral artery disease (PAD) is related to narrowing of the peripheral arterial diameter. Lower-extremity atherosclerotic PAD is the most common clinical presentation in daily practice. Over 200 million people are suffering from PAD worldwide which is associated with mortality [1], [2]. Patients with PAD are in higher risk for cardiovascular disease, all-cause mortality, myocardial infarction and stroke, even if they have been treated for classic atherosclerotic risk factors [3]. PAD is also diagnosed when the ankle-brachial index (ABI) ≤ 0.90 , while the normal ABI ranges from 1.00 to 1.40. ABI values higher than 1.3 indicate calcified or

noncompressible arteries often present in patients with diabetes or chronic kidney disease [4]. ABI is a simple clinical test that compares the blood pressure in the upper and lower limbs and is usually suggested to be measured in patients with symptoms. However, it is also useful for premature diagnosis and treatment in patients without symptoms. Specifically, the ABI index is suitable for checking PAD and assessing risk of cardiovascular disease in asymptomatic adults [5].

It was observed that 11% of PAD patients have usually critical limb ischemia, a serious outcome of PAD [6]. Moreover, the risk of limb loss can reach 10–40% in one year [7]. Undiagnosed PAD in patients is able to lead in serious complications and the urgent need of interventions. Critical consequences of PAD are limb amputation and peripheral artery revascularization. Revascularization in combination with medical treatment assist in the decrease of amputation rates in patients with limb ischemia [8].

A significant risk factor for PAD is hypertension. Patients with arterial hypertension have an increased risk of lower limb revascularization and amputation, due to a higher incidence of peripheral artery disease. Atherosclerotic disease is often present in these patients. However, the impact of hypertension on cardiovascular and limb events in PAD patients, such as acute limb ischemia, amputation or peripheral revascularization, is not fully understood [9], [10].

The study of Valentine [11], examined the variety and quantity of lower extremity amputations or revascularization surgeries necessary throughout the 4-year follow-up period. The study was conducted in 51 white men <45 years who developed PAD symptoms. The study found that patients who grow PAD before the age of 43 are more likely to require multiple medical interventions. Even though 60% of patients with premature PAD who were referred to a vascular surgery service appeared to have stable conditions, 40% of them would require multiple interventions due to disease progression or bypass graft failure. Furthermore, the composite endpoint of vessel revascularization or lower limb amputation was studied

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as a primary outcome in another study [12]. They analysed 101 patients with 76 years mean age and 68 % of them being hypertensive. Additionally, over a median time of 14 months, they observed 29 events. Moreover, they used features such as cardiovascular risk factors, baseline total and differential white blood cells counts, and angiographic data. They discovered that the neutrophil count may be a good indicator of the severity of atherosclerosis and tissue damage and could help doctors spot patients with advanced peripheral vascular disease who need more aggressive treatment. Additionally, 12,206 patients with newly diagnosed PAD between 1998 and 2008 were used to identify the predictors for peripheral revascularization procedures (PRP) or nontraumatic lower extremity amputations (LEA) [13]. There were 150 patients who underwent LEA, PRP, or both procedures out of the total number of patients (81 LEA, 53 PRP, 16 both PRP and LEA). The risk factors for both procedures were age, male gender, and a history of coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, or atrial fibrillation hospitalizations, according to the analysis.

In this work, we aim to predict the need of amputation and/or peripheral artery revascularization in hypertensive patients with 7 years follow-up using the getABI study cohort. We specifically used three machine learning models, with Random Forest producing the best metrics. The novelty of this work lies in its application of 12 daily clinical features that predict the need of two serious medical procedures, the amputation and peripheral revascularization.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Workflow

In our analysis, the followed workflow included 4 main stages. In the first stage, the data of the getABI study were pre-processed. In the second step, feature selection was performed and three machine learning models were applied in the third stage. The final step included the estimation of the models' performance and the explanation of the results. Fig. 1 depicts the overall workflow with more details at each stage of the analysis.

Figure 1. The overall workflow that was followed in the current prediction.

B. Data description

In this work, the data utilized come from the German epidemiological trial on ankle brachial index - getABI cohort [14]. It includes 6,474 patients with age of 65 years and older. Moreover, it contains demographics, medicines, comorbidities, laboratory and clinical data. Various endpoints were also included, which are associated with cardiovascular disease and death in different follow up. In our study, we selected 53 variables from the initial dataset and 6,459

patients (15 patients were excluded due to missing values). During the 7 years of follow-up, 182 patients underwent either amputation or revascularization or both. The final dataset was created selecting only the hypertensive patients thus 4,191 hypertensive patients were included, from which 150 patients underwent either amputation or revascularization or both within 7 years follow-up.

C. Data pre-processing

One of the important steps for prediction of events using machine learning algorithms is data pre-processing. In our analysis we applied the following techniques: cleaning, statistical analysis, conversion of features type to appropriate ones, selection of the hypertensive patients, hyperparameter tuning, feature selection, creation of the balanced dataset and splitting of the dataset.

The model hyperparameters were optimized using the GridSearchCV algorithm and extracting the appropriate parameters of each based on 10-fold cross-validation (CV). Moreover, the down sampling method is applied when the two classes of the target feature are unbalanced. In our analysis, the class 0 consists of 4,041 patients while the class 1 includes only 150. As a result, we kept all of the data from the minority class 1, while randomly selecting an equal number of samples from the majority class 0. This procedure ends when the majority and minority class samples are balanced, in order to create a new balanced 1:1 ratio dataset for additional analysis. The final analysis was conducted in 150 patients who underwent the double endpoint and 150 random healthy individuals for 300 iterations. Subsequently, the dataset was splitted into 85 % training set to train the model and 15 % testing set to check the accuracy of the models.

D. Feature selection

Feature selection was conducted employing Extremely Randomized Trees Classifier (Extra Trees Classifier) for selecting the most predominant features. The ExtraTreesClassifier is an ensemble tree-based machine learning approach that relies on randomization to reduce variance, computational cost and execution time [15].

Figure 2. Top 10 important features selected by ExtraTreesClassifier.

Age and gender are included in the analysis as they are major risk factors. Therefore, the 10 most important features were selected among 53, namely daily habits, medicines, comorbidities, clinical and laboratory data (Fig. 2), in which the models were iteratively trained and evaluated (GFR_MDRD, smoking status, ABI index before exercise,

HbA1c, Dorsalis pedis left artery, Troponin I, NT-proBNP, Creatinine, CSE inhibitors and Glucose). The final dataset contained 12 attributes, for which the machine learning models were trained. These features and their descriptive statistics for all patients are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. THE PERFORMANCE OF EACH MACHINE LEARNING MODEL.

No.	Attributes of analysis		
	Name of feature	Mean value/Percentage	S/D
1	Age	72.8	5.335
2	Sex	59.2% Female & 40.8 % Male	-
3	GFR_MDRD	82.79	19.825
4	Smoking Status	54.7 % Non-smoker, 37.3 % Ex-smoker, 7.9 % Active	-
5	ABI index before exercise	1.0099	0.187
6	HbA1c	5.74	0.991
7	Dorsalis Pedis Left Artery	69.4 % Easily palpable, 21.3 % weakly palpable, 9.0 % not palpable	-
8	Troponin I	12.74	89.627
9	N-Terminal pro-Brain Natriuretic Peptide	319.61	598.326
10	Creatinine	0.86	0.262
11	CSE inhibitors (statins)	22.6 % Yes & 77.3 % No	-
12	Glucose	51.98	36.943

E. Supervised machine learning models and their performance

Three supervised machine learning models, Random Forest (RF) [16], Extreme Gradient Boost (XGBoost) [17] and Adaptive Boost (AdaBoost) [18] were selected. Their performance was calculated using standard metrics, namely Accuracy Sensitivity, Specificity and the Receiver Operative Characteristic Curve (ROC) and the Area under the ROC curve (AUC).

F. Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (xAI) was used in our analysis in order to explain the significance of implemented features [19]. Specifically, we utilized the SHAP-Shapley Additive exPlanations method, which contains the TreeSHAP, an efficient estimation approach for tree-based models [20].

III. RESULTS

The current study was conducted using Python and the library scikit-learn. The performance of each model was estimated after 300 iterated runs, extracting mean values of the metrics. Table II presents the performance of the three machine learning algorithms.

The results of experiments were evaluated and compared in order to identify the best predictive model for the need of amputation and/or peripheral artery revascularization in

hypertensive patients. Random Forest achieved the highest mean values of accuracy and sensitivity equal to 73.27 % and 71.62 %, respectively. It also achieved 75.20 % specificity. In addition, the low difference of sensitivity and specificity values of this model proves that our analysis was carried out with a balanced dataset. On the other hand, AdaBoost model achieved the lower performance metrics equal to 72.92 % of accuracy and 70.53 of sensitivity.

TABLE II. THE PERFORMANCE OF EACH MACHINE LEARNING MODEL.

ML models	Performance Evaluation			
	Accuracy %	Sensitivity %	Specificity %	AUC
XGBoost	73.02	69.22	77.37	73.29
RF	73.27	71.62	75.20	73.39
AdaBoost	72.92	70.53	75.67	73.10

a. Sample of a Table footnote. (Table footnote)

Moreover, the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves are shown in Fig. 3. Random Forest achieved the highest AUC mean value equal to 73.39 %. On the other hand, AdaBoost scored 73.10 %, which was the lowest of all.

Figure 3. The mean values of area under receiver operating characteristic curve for the three classifiers after 300 iterations.

Figure 4. Feature importance according to mean SHAP value.

In our analysis, we applied the TreeSHAP explainer with Random Forest model as such emerged as the most accurate. The most significant features according to the absolute average of the SHAP values are presented in Fig. 4. The red bar and the blue bar represent the class 1 and the class 0 of

our target feature, respectively. ABI before exercise was the most important feature in the prediction of double endpoint achieving the highest SHAP values, especially for class 1. On the other hand, the CSE inhibitors exhibit the lowest impact on the analysis presenting the lowest SHAP values. Moreover, dorsalis pedis left artery, HbA1c, glucose and N-terminal pro-Brain Natriuretic Peptide make up the top five most important features.

IV. CONCLUSION

Hypertension is a crucial risk factor for PAD, hence we predict the need for peripheral artery revascularization and/or amputation in hypertensive patients after 7 years follow-up using just 12 daily clinical and laboratory features. XGBoost, Random Forest, AdaBoost were employed for this purpose. In addition, contemporary techniques were utilized such as hyperparameter tuning, to increase the performance. Furthermore, the down-sampling method was applied in order to create a balanced dataset and the performance of each model was estimated after 300 consecutive iterations extracting average metrics, thus increasing the robustness of our methodology. The results were compared and showed that the Random Forest model outperformed all the others, achieving the highest mean accuracy and sensitivity 73.27 % and 71.62 % respectively. Finally, we used the SHAP plot to show the importance and the impact of each feature on the prediction.

The novelty is related to the analysis of an important and life changing clinical event in this large and highly sensitive group of patients, which has not been analysed before using ML. The early identification of amputation and peripheral artery revascularization assists clinicians in administering timely treatment (i.e. anti-hypertensive drugs, statins, etc) to avoid further disease progression. Our main objective was to predict these endpoints using various machine learning techniques and to compare them all to find the most accurate computational model for prediction. Testing multiple ML models for efficiency in endpoint prediction allows to select the most appropriate one, based on the available data. Thus, our analysis can be used as a prognostic tool for the patients and physicians.

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